

Achieving Traceability within Supply Chains through Data Science

ER RAQABI El Mehdi

Abstract

The topic of my conference presentation is related to data science and the role it can "play to solve traceability issues in supply chain management. Falsification is a significant risk within any supply chain. The longer the process or the chain, the higher the risk that the customer gets a falsified product or service. Including data science as a tool to extract knowledge may provide insights about the crucial points where the falsification process of products and services takes place within a supply chain. In several papers, this problem is discussed and the main methods used are RFID (Radio Frequency Identification) and CSFs (Critical Success Factors) as well as the emerging block chain technology. The data science, machine learning, and artificial intelligence aspects remain less discovered compared to others and provide a high potential to solve the traceability issue. By incorporating data science and robots in crucial falsification points within a supply chain, traceability can be achieved. Robot Will either achieve the tasks with high falsification risk or inspect the output of these tasks once achieved by humans. If the products and services contain unique features that robots can learn through supervised learning and which humans cannot easily falsify, falsification risk can be significantly reduced. By achieving a robot level performance that is higher than the human level performance on this aspect, it will become difficult to unethical people to falsify products and services and their originality will be consequently maintained and sustained.

February 20, 2019